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Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method

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1. Interface as the key element in structural interventions.

Retrofitting schemes using composites consist of application to an existing cross-section, concrete or steel, Fiber Reinforced Polymer systems with various chemical or mechanical means (*see Deliverable D4*). The added FRP is the new reinforcement to bear tension loads. The plane of the two surfaces in contact is the so-called interface. This part of the composite cross-section is the key element to an effective intervention. This is because of its role, which is to transfer loads from the substrate, that is existing concrete or steel, to the composite material. This creates many issues to be solved, for instance what is the integration level of the FRP system to the existing substrate, what are the relative slips- if any, what is the failure mechanism and the crack pattern and the level of the transferred load to the added material.

A retrofitted cross-section is expected to function monolithically, with no significant failures and slips, especially on the compression zone. It is commonly accepted that the concrete (substrate) is considered as the weakest link of a strengthening system. Especially, if the substrate bears initial damages (extensive cracking) or is exposed to extreme conditions and therefore needs repair, e.g. due to corrosion cracks, it is expected to initiate the failure mechanism of the strengthening scheme. The example of corrosion is a commonly real problem met both in buildings or infrastructure assets. The crack initiation of corrosion creates a crack pattern due to the opening in parallel to the reinforcement rebars and reduces the tensile strength of concrete [1], [2], [3], [4]. Therefore influences the bond of the substrate and the strengthening system [5], [6], which is crucial to fulfil the threshold of EN 1504 Standard [8] of tensile concrete strength equal to 1.5MPa [7]. As such, the interaction of the substrate and the adhesive layer is crucial since it is the path expected to function properly in order to transfer loads to the FRP material.

The modern design regulations for interventions in structures, describe the design of the retrofitted cross section, but they do not refer extensively to the failure mechanism or how the load is transferred at the interface and therefore the integration level of the intervention material to the substrate. Such an approach needs proper quantification of the force transferred through the interface level and an index to describe the efficiency of the interface to transfer loads and their failure modes. In most regulations and codes, especially seismic design ones, damage indices are dimensionless parameters ranging between 0 (undamaged) to 1 (fully damaged/collapse). The earliest damage indices were mostly based on displacement/rotational ductility (μ_θ) or the flexural damage, part of them taking into consideration the degradation of strength and stiffness due to the propagating cracking and damage, or combined also with dissipated energy and cumulative hysteretic demand [15], [16]. The estimations of such indexes have been compared also with experimental works, whereas there is limited- if any work for such indexes referring to retrofitting structural members. There are only a few examples of codes that identify the problem of interfaces, quantifying the problem of integration by incorporating monolithic factors [17], [18] there is no specific reference to the use of composite materials.

Indexes of quantification of the response or damage for structural members are very useful in the continuous monitoring of the performance. Especially, in the assessment procedures, these indexes can enrich the data selection of the so-called performance indicators (PI) and depict the structural integrity of the member and moreover the structure itself [19]. However, there are no indexes proposed for the response of the significant part of the retrofitting, that is the interface, and how it helps the substrate to integrate the added material.

Towards the direction of monitoring and predicting the substrate's failure propagation especially with different kind of matrices, this research proposes a novel index to quantify the efficiency of the interface. The research includes retrofitting schemes using composite materials, Fiber Reinforced Polymers (FRP) and different adhesives layers to bond them externally in reinforced concrete substrates (*see Deliverable D7*). The interfaces are very sensitive to elastic strains and deflections and as such a proper monitoring method was chosen to detect discontinuities, deflections and overstressed areas, as well as to quantify the activated area of the retrofitting measures.

2. Description of efficiency parameters- proposed methodology.

2.1 Capacity in transferring loads

The capacity of the strengthening system to transfer loads depends heavily on the type of the FRP applied and the connection layer, mostly used epoxy adhesives, as well as the initial structural integrity of the concrete substrate in which it will be embedded. Theoretically, the integration of the FRP system creates a monolithical cross-section in which the composite plays the role of the externally bonded-reinforcement. Though, due to the relative slip between the connected materials and the potential or progressive crack opening at the concrete substrate, this is not fully feasible [13]. A full integration would mean that the force is gradually transferred to the FRP on the whole with no abrupt failures of the elements of the system, e.g. concrete, adhesive layer or debonding, and the cross-section would continue to bear stress and strains. A low integration level would denote that once the strengthening system starts bearing loads, premature failure, that is debonding occurs. The integration level can also be reduced due to the existence of undesirable particles on the surface of the application of the retrofitting measure, even if properly cleaned according to technical specifications. This can be the result e.g. of corrosion, especially if the retrofitting has been applied at the very early stages and products continue to leach. Corrosion is a commonly met problem in infrastructure assets and structural members causing tremendous resistance reduction, restoration problems, even failures. A proper quantification of the integration level is needed for all types of structural integrity substrates. connect with assessment.

2.2 Capacity of limiting failure propagation

The failure propagation at the substrate level is crucial. The strain distribution and the crack opening creates discontinuities and disruptions at the load flow path. As such, the crack propagation decreases the integration level and the monolithicity of the interface of the retrofitted cross-section. The type of the FRP strengthening measure chosen indicates the development of different crack patterns under overloading conditions. For example, stiffer FRP such as prefabricated plates present a brittle debonding failure mode, whereas in FRP laminated fabrics strengthening solutions there are less abrupt force disruptions due to the crack propagation. This kind of crack and stress distribution along the interface vary also when different kind of matrices are used. Toughened adhesives that connect the composites and concrete can limit the dislocations and absorb more energy enhancing the efficiency of the intervention.

2.3 Efficiency indices

The quantification of the interface efficiency derives from: (a) the capacity in transferring loads to the composite material and (b) to the damage dislocation from the substrate (concrete) to the connection layer (epoxy adhesive). The expression of this quantification is the proposed Interface Capacity index (IC) given by equation (1):

$$IF_c = \{a \cdot IC_L + \beta \cdot IC_{fp}\} \quad (1)$$

The coefficients a and β represent the substrate's initial condition: coefficient a equals to 1 in cases where the integrity is not affected and corresponds to a fully healthy concrete element. The value can fall up to 0.8 when for e.g. corrosion has initiated and the products are obvious at the surface of the element. Coefficient β expresses the existence of initial cracks. The values of β ranges from 0.7-1. It is equivalent to 1 when the initial cracking is of limited width ($w=0-0.35$ mm) whereas can fall up to 0.7 in cases that the cracks' width is larger than 1 mm.

The IC index is the sum of the two different factors, IC_L for the interface capacity in transferring loads and IC_{fp} for the interface capacity of damage dislocation that are described in equations (2) and (3) below:

$$IC_L = \sqrt{L_e \cdot \frac{t_r}{t_f} \cdot \frac{f_f}{f_r}} \quad (2)$$

$$IC_{fp} = \frac{E_r}{E_f} \cdot \frac{L_e \times W_e}{d \cdot 1000} \quad (3)$$

The factor L_e corresponds to the effective bond length of the composite material and is adopted according to the Eurocode 8 regulation [14] and is given by equation (4):

$$L_e = \sqrt{\frac{E_f \cdot t_f}{4 \cdot f_{ctm}}} \quad (4)$$

and W_e corresponds to the active width of the composite and it is assumed to be decreased per 20% of the initial width (see Section 4.2). In the above equations t_r and t_f are the epoxy and composite's thickness, f_r and f_f are the tensile strength, E_r and E_f are the moduli of elasticity for the epoxy adhesive layer and the FRP respectively, and lastly f_{ctm} is the tensile strength of concrete. Finally, d corresponds to the height of the cross section where the FRP is applied.

3. SHM methods to quantify efficiency of interfaces: guided waves.

As mentioned and described thoroughly in the report of Deliverable D5 there are many techniques to monitor the displacements, strains and changes of a structure. The different methods are based on a different technology and function principles, one of which is the guided waves. In combination with the advanced technology sensors and probes guided waves gather a lot of attention due to the advantages compared to the other non-destructive (NDT) approaches. In inspections and damage detection, guided waves are capable of diagnosing in the long-distance or inaccessible areas or interest with either pitch-catch method or the pulse-echo method [20]. They have neglectable interaction with electromagnetic signals, making them suitable in many industries, and their use and application is very simple as well as low cost. This benefit of rapid and wide screening that they are able to provide makes them efficient to be used for real time and continuous monitoring (see Deliverable D8).

The scattering of waves after their interaction with defects or different solid media can help to predict and characterize any potential damages, discontinuities or voids or the cracking propagation, as well as overloaded areas and regions of increased risk to fail or collapse. The data of such methods can be further processed and if combined with appropriate algorithms or mathematical elaborations (Fourier-Transform) they are able to provide imaging of high accuracy even three-dimensional. This approach is very helpful in bridge application despite the higher computational cost, due to the importance of the asset and the simplicity of the method.

The main disadvantage of the method, except for the experienced surveyors to apply it, is that further characterisation requires, in most cases, further documentation and tests for result validation, that is, semi/non-destructive testing (NDT). The characterisation of damages often is challenging. For example, if wave propagation and ultrasonic methods are used for detecting, mapping and characterising damages within assets, the interpretation of the scattering field or the decomposition of the wave modes or conversion of waveforms into data, in time or frequency domain is time-consuming and complex [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], as well as most of the times amplification of results is needed. This means that further processing if needed based on the geometry and the mechanical properties of the asset or the interoperabilities of the network, as well as the real-time noise that needs to be extracted.

This study adopts the wave propagation method to monitor the interface response of CFRP retrofitted reinforced concrete substrates, belonging to RC bridges' decks' structural members (Figure 1) by exciting an elastic wave. Such method can detect damages (cracks) of fatigue [21], [22], corrosion [23], [24], or delamination/debonding type [25]. The layers are not considered perfectly bonded, materials are distinctly attributed with properties, as well as the interface layer consists of a separate model calibrated further by tests. The scope was to determine the active length and width of the strengthening measure and to make use of it for the Interface Capacity Indices confirming the response and the failure of each strengthening system through the path figure of the wave excitation along the axis of the structural member (see Section 4.3).

Figure 1. Damages in retrofitting schemes using composite materials applied in concrete bridges.

4. Results.

4.1 Finite element simulation.

Reinforced concrete (RC) pedestrian bridges of highways commonly present failures and are considered as decaying structures, needing strengthening. This work studied the diagnosis of a beam of rectangular cross section (Figure 2a) of a pedestrian RC bridge deck numerically, using guided waves. One of the most common strengthening schemes using composite materials is the FRP prefabricated plates, externally bonded on the concrete bottom surface as a tensile external reinforcement (see also Deliverable D4), which was assigned to the model (Figure 2b). The beam was designed according to Eurocodes and was simulated using Ansys software.

The interface of the retrofitted structural element was simulated using cohesive zone models. The Cohesive Zone Models (CZM) have been extensively used to simulate the fracture of ductile and brittle solids [34], the delamination of composites from substrates [35] and the behaviour of adhesively bonded composites [36], [35][37], [38], [39]. These models consist of a constitutive relation between stresses of the interface and the corresponding interfacial relative displacements (slip) of the connected materials. They simulate the elastic response up to the peak load, initiation of damage and further propagation due to local failure of a material/contact, sometimes followed by a softening response, to model the gradual degradation of material properties up to complete failure. The areas of the CZM correspond to the fracture energy needed for failure. Mode II debonding represents a mode of separation of the interface where tangential slip dominates the separation normal to the interface.

The debonding of FRP composites applied to the concrete substrate was simulated with a numerical model developed using the commercial software ANSYS. For the realistic representation and simulation of the failure modes of the FRP strengthened concrete substrates a bilinear CZM fracture model (Figure 3) was used and calibrated from the experimental results. Concrete and CFRPs were treated as homogeneous isotropic linear-elastic materials and were connected through zero thickness interfaces. Concrete and composites were simulated using a 3-d solid element, defined by eight nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node: translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions.

Model calibration is a cornerstone for the FE model in order to have credibility. This is achieved by comparing with the test data (see extensively in Deliverable D7). The calibration, in which a minimum deviation within acceptable limits is met, between the FEM results and the corresponding test data, is an optimization process with many parameters to consider, with deviation metrics that are usually nonlinear [40], [41]. In this study, the calibration was achieved in two stages: first the mechanical parameters of the adhesive (linear) were defined and second, the failure mode (nonlinear) mechanism.

The diagnosis of the capacity of the interface to transfer loads was simulated with a transient analysis of shear waves. Guided waves present good sensitivity when interacting with discontinuities and are good to detect overloading areas, especially in bonded structural elements. Conventional inspections

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with ultrasonic guided waves of these multilayer structures is very difficult due to numerous wave reflections and mode conversions at boundaries. At low frequencies, mode-converted and reflected waves superimpose to produce Lamb waves [43]. The dispersive character of these waves makes them sensitive to local changes of thickness or material properties. Making them ideal to be used to investigate bonding and interfacial properties by interpreting results based on the dispersion curves. Despite this, interpreting the reflections and transmissions of these waves is challenging and complex for multi-layered structures such as retrofitted concrete substrates due to multiple resonances [44].

Detailed understanding of wave interactions with defects can be of use in the model-based definition of a procedure for defect characterization based on the scattering response [45], [46]. The ability to describe the variation of scattering coefficients as a function of the characteristics of the interface is fundamental to define a strategy to solve the inverse problem, and it can also help to select modes and frequencies that improve the inspection sensitivity to various changes due to overloading, debondings and disruptions of load transfer. From a practical point of view, the SH0 mode is nondispersive and can be applied to both plates and pipes because its dynamics also satisfactorily describe the behavior of the first torsional mode in pipes of large radii.

For all above, the simulation was simplified only to the substrate of the concrete cover and the CFRP plate externally bonded with different epoxies of a simply supported beam of the deck. Figure 4 report the dispersion relation of shear waves, showing group (a) and phase velocity (b) as a function of the thickness-frequency product $2hf$ (in $MHz\ mm$), with frequency f (in Hz). The plot refers to the CFRP plate that was used in the analyses, with the following parameters: $\rho = 2810\ kg/m^3$, $\mu = 27,000\ MPa$, and $\lambda = 55,000\ MPa$. Longitudinal and shear velocities were respectively equal to $c_L = 6200\ m/s$ and $c_T = 3071\ m/s$.

Figure 2. Finite element simulation of a) the cross section of a beam and b) the concrete substrate of a beam belonging to the deck of a pedestrian bridge,

Figure 3. Bilinear CZM model for interface simulation.

Figure 4. Shear waves dispersion curves for CFRP: a) group and b) phase velocity.

4.2 Scattering field.

Based on the scattering field, the guided waves were used to explain, understand and quantify the efficiency of the interfaces, the following equations (Eq.1-3) are a simplified approach of understanding the scattering field of the layered structural element [47]:

$$I_{int} = \frac{A_I^C - A_I^{FRP}}{A_I^h} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$R_{int} = \frac{A_R^C - A_R^{FRP}}{A_R^h} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$T_{int} = \frac{A_T^C - A_T^{FRP}}{A_T^h} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

where, I stands for the incident wave (the position of the excitation), R stands for the reflections, T for the transmissions. Superscript C refers to concrete substrate, FRP to the FRP measure, h refers to the undamaged (healthy) beam, whereas the subscripts int refers to the interface.

This approach differentiates the scattering field, that is the amplitude of the transmissions, reflections and the instant wave that travels to the layered element. From these results it is obvious that the measurements in distinct points and with one frequency, the results can be vague. The amplitude alone is not capable of making results for the interface level. Also, the time histories can be confusing (Figures 6-9). The wave packets indicate clearly a damaged area, though the type of damage, e.g. discontinuity or debonding length is not straightforward quantified and as such the integrity of the interface is not evaluated specifically, nor the risk of debonding is quantified in order to define the integration level. The interactions at the boundaries of the different materials complicates the results as well as the waveform which is shifted from the first symmetric to multiple and higher order modes, also shifting the frequency of the excitation along its travel. Further decomposition of the scattering field, based on the different velocities, interactions and dispersion diagrams, would be of use to interpret the results and make conclusions for the damage detection and characterisation or mapping. within the different density materials would increase the computational cost and would need experts' consultancy.

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Figure 5. Damages in retrofitting schemes using composite materials in concrete bridges decks.

Figure 6. Displacement Field of varying crack depth (a) Incident Location (b) Before the discontinuity (c) After the Discontinuity

Figure 7. Displacement field at characteristic locations along the beam (a) No damage (b) 10 mm crack (c) 20 mm crack (d) 30mm crack

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Figure 8. Displacement Field of various debonding length (a) Incident Location (b) Before the discontinuity (c) After the Discontinuity

Figure 9. Displacement field at characteristic locations along the beam (a) No damage (b) 50 mm debonding (c) 10 mm debonding length (d) 200 mm debonding length.

Further parametric investigation was conducted numerically in two phases. The first phase of the analysis was (a) static causing the maximum shear strain at the interface and second (b) a dynamic transient to quantify the overloaded areas of the interface and the CFRP activated area. Also, a parametric study was performed to investigate on the influence of a minor flexural crack at the wave propagation along the interface.

The results show that there is clear superposition of the waves and change in waveform at the interface level (Figure 10a). The results in terms of displacements between the different epoxies used differentiate

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based on the stiffness and elastic properties of the epoxies. Epoxy Sikadur 370 is a toughened epoxy with considerably lower modulus of Elasticity in respect to the standard epoxies (Sikadur 30 and Sikadur 33). Further information on the epoxies are developed in the report D7. Though, in the stress field (Figure 10, results denote the concentration of the load in the middle cross section and relate to the properties of the interface layer. The more toughened epoxies (Figure 10b-iii) present a shift of the waveform close to the overloaded area, whereas the standard epoxies present no significant changes and are more uniform along the width of the strengthening measure.

In practice, the accessible part to make the measurement is the bottom layer of the CFRP plate. The stress allocation is shown in Figure 10c. Locally close to the overloaded area, the bottom layer of the FRP plate is also stressed according to the interface elastic properties. As illustrated in Figure 10c-iii, the more toughened the adhesive layer is, the more activated is the FRP plate. There are small areas where stresses concentrate and initiate the brittle failure, starting from the boundaries of the CFRP plate. The toughened epoxies present more areas of concentrated stresses, which means that the limits are exceeded and debonding occurs. Practically, approximately 20% of the CFRP plates in all cases work beyond the limits and as such, the effective width W_e factor's value of *Section 2.3* is confirmed.

Figure 10. Contour plots of the transient diagnostic analysis with ultrasonic guided shear waves in a concrete substrate retrofitted with CFRP prefabricated plate no cracking: a) wave propagation at the interface level, b) stress allocation at the interface level, c) stress allocation at the bottom side of the CFRP plate.

At the presence of a small flexural crack (Figure 11) there is a disturbance at the wave propagation (Figure 12a). There is a conversion and superposition of multiple higher order wave modes due to the interaction with the crack's lips. The stress concentration at the interface level (Figure 12b) depends on the epoxy layer. The less tough the epoxy is (Figure 12c-i) the more uniform the stress distribution is. In this case, the failure of the interface initiates from the middle axis of the area, whereas, at the case of the toughened epoxies (Figure 12c-iii), the failure propagates faster to the boundaries of the area, resulting in more brittle response.

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Figure 11. Flexural cracking at the middle cross-section of the simply supported FEM model- depth a) 50% and b) 67% of the cover height.

Figure 12. Contour plots of the transient diagnostic analysis with ultrasonic guided shear waves in a concrete substrate retrofitted with CFRP prefabricated plate with flexural crack opened in the middle cross-section: a) wave propagation at the interface level, b) stress allocation at the interface level, c) stress allocation at the bottom side of the CFP plate.

4.3 Force transfer.

The integration percentage of the prefabricated plates is investigated with the observation of the path diagrams at the end of each step of the analysis, that is static and transient. The path diagrams show the transfer of loads from layer to layer along the length of the FEM model [48], in two different paths, one on the boundary and one on the central axis. The paths illustrated in Figures 13-16 show the vertical displacements, the stresses and the sliding in three different levels: i) concrete substrate, ii) CFRP plate and iii) adhesive layer.

At the end of the static analysis (Figure 13) the cross section with the maximum deflection presents the peak of the curves for all different epoxies. The stresses of the CFRP bottom layer (Figure 13 j-l) and the epoxy layer are complementary to each other. They denote the force transfer happening through the interface and the stress flow between the concrete substrate and the FRP plate (Figure 13 j-l). For the cases that the substrate is more toughened, the force of the interface as well as the transferred stress at the FRP plate is much larger, the sliding distance and displacement are larger and result in more energy absorbed by the interface layer before debonding. It is remarkable that the toughened epoxies present more brittle response since the sliding values are larger (Figure 13n-o).

The two different paths, one at the boundary of the specimen simulated and one at the central axis have differences mainly at the FRP layer (Figure 14). They denote the failure propagation, which seems to start from the boundaries (path B). The toughened epoxies absorb on average 3-5 times larger energy (Figure 14 g-i) and also the sliding of the interface is 8 times larger compared to the standard epoxies (Figure 14 j-l).

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Figure 13. Path diagrams- first analysis' phase (static): vertical displacements for the concrete substrate (a-c), for the CFPR (d-f), for the interface layer (g-i) and sliding of the interface (j-l).

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Figure 14. Path diagrams- second analysis' phase (transient): vertical displacements for contact at the (a-c), for the CFPR (d-f), for the interface (g-i) and sliding for the interface layer (j-l).

Results for the case that the model has a flexural crack opened at the middle cross section, the results are illustrated in Figures 15-18. For both depths of the crack, the results are analogous to the non-cracked concrete substrate. It is clearly noted that the sliding in these cases is one order of magnitude higher than the undamaged concrete layer and result in much faster debonding, especially for the toughened layer.

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Figure 15. Path diagrams- second analysis' phase (transient) - damaged model- crack depth 673%: interface layer vertical displacements (a-c) and sliding (c-e).

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Figure 16. Path diagrams- damaged model- crack depth 67%- second analysis' phase (transient): interface layer vertical displacements (a-c) and sliding (c-e).

Figure 17. Path diagrams- second analysis' phase (transient)- damaged model- crack depth 50%:- interface layer vertical displacements (a-c) and sliding (c-e).

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Figure 18. Path diagrams- second analysis' phase (transient) - damaged model- crack depth 50% -: vertical displacements for the concrete substrate (a-c), for the CFPR (d-f), for the interface (g-i) and sliding for the interface layer (j-l).

5. Conclusions.

This report concludes to the following points:

- The interface capacity consists of two parameters: a) the capacity of transferring loads and b) the failure propagation. The study proposes a novel model for the quantification of the interface capacity and the prediction of the failure mode of concrete elements strengthened with composite measures (brittle or pseudo-plastic).
- The guided waves can help to quantify the integration and efficiency level of the measure by depicting the stresses and sliding or displacement in order to identify the failure initiation and propagation.
- This method help to quantify the effective width of the strengthening measure and can be further used to identify the kind extension of a crack or multiple ones.

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